

1 **Tumor cells undergo activation of ERBB2 upon entry and migration to the periphery in human**
2 **prostate cancer.**

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7 We recently provided among the first basic total descriptions of the circulating tumor cell in humans with
8 cancer, isolated from humans with stage IV breast cancer. Here, we study total transcription in circulating
9 tumor cells (CTC) isolated from humans with prostate cancer, associated with a high rate of metastasis to
10 the lymph nodes and skeletal system. We observed activation of ERBB2 in the CTC, during migration to
11 the periphery in humans with prostate cancer. The data demonstrate and reflect an unprecedented role
12 for the human epidermal growth factor (HER) family gene ERBB2 in multiple steps of the solid tumor life
13 cycle: in migration to the CNS in women with breast cancer, and migration to the bones in men with
14 prostate cancer.

15 **References**

16 1. Würth, Roberto et al. "Circulating tumor cell plasticity determines breast cancer therapy resistance
17 via neuregulin 1-HER3 signaling." Nature cancer vol. 6,1 (2025): 67-85. doi:10.1038/s43018-024-00882-2
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